

Some issues of legal regulation of contractual relations on the Internet

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Abstract: the article characterizes the issues of legal regulation of contractual relations on the Internet, the essence and significance of transactions concluded therein, their specific features, and reveals some issues and legal conflicts that arise during electronic data exchange.

Key words: electronic commerce, transactions, contracts, electronic data exchange, electronic digital signature, authentication, transaction forms, innovations, information society, electronic commerce.

In our country, the development of digital technologies, the digital economy, is one of the key priorities of state policy, defined by the Development Strategy of the New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026, where one of the goals is the development of the digital economy as the main “driver” with an increase in its volume by at least 2.5 times.

It should be noted that in Uzbekistan in recent years of reforms in the field of digital economy development, such important acts as the Resolutions and Decrees of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On measures to accelerate the development of electronic commerce” dated May 14, 2018, “On measures to widely implement the digital economy and electronic government” dated April 28, 2020, have been adopted, "On measures to fundamentally improve contractual relations" dated September 14, 2021, "On improving the administration of e-commerce and creating favorable conditions for its further development" dated November 17, 2021, as well as the Strategy "Digital Uzbekistan-2030".

It is also encouraging that “On the establishment of the Cyber University”, adopted by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 20, 2025, for the purpose of training personnel in the field of information protection, information and cybersecurity, the creation of automated information and analytical systems based on artificial intelligence, robotics, and related areas, retraining and advanced training of specialists in the field of digital technologies.

Despite significant progress in recent years, in our country, there is a need for further regulatory support for these legal relations, paying more attention to issues of legal

regulation of contractual relations on the Internet.

Indeed, information technologies have changed the structure of relationships between business entities and the mechanisms of doing business in the world. Thus, according to international reports, at the beginning of the 20s, e-commerce accounted for 18% of the total volume of retail sales in the world, and the turnover of e-commerce reached about 5 trillion US dollars. In addition, just recently, the pandemic situation in the world has led to a sharp expansion of the electronic market. Due to the increase in the share of electronic commerce, the need for further regulatory support and legal regulation of transactions carried out in it has also increased. Consequently, the rapid development of Information Technology (IT) in the last two to three decades has led to the emergence of new social relations that are developing in a special information environment – the Internet.

The category of contracts in the sphere of electronic commerce fits into the existing system of civil law contracts and does not require the introduction of additional definitions. At the same time, it cannot be denied that the conclusion and execution of these contracts also have their own specifics.

When analyzing the subject composition of relations in the sphere of electronic relations and the qualification of its types on this basis, the peculiarity of such a special category of participants in electronic commerce as information intermediaries is revealed. These persons send, receive or store potentially valuable information, facilitate the conclusion (execution) of electronic contracts, and also provide other related services, for example, organize electronic data exchange. Moreover, at present, such a phenomenon as artificial intelligence (AI) and questions of its possible legal capacity in relation to issues of e-commerce are acquiring great importance. It seems that artificial intelligence itself cannot be a subject of civil law, since it can only be considered as a certain object of legal relations. Accordingly, the legal consequences resulting from the actions of artificial intelligence should be borne by its owners and/or operators.

In addition, a significant portion of contracts are concluded by robot programs without human participation. In the material space, it is not uncommon to use vending machines - machines when concluding a public contract (for example, a vending machine for selling drinks, etc.).

The Internet also uses electronic analogues of machines - robot programs that help to draw up, conclude and except for execution a contract. In some countries, this creates uncertainty regarding the validity of contracts concluded by robot programs without direct human participation, which raises doubts about the subject's expression of will. These

doubts are based on the fact that the robot program could have malfunctioned; or unauthorized access could have been obtained to the robot program, which resulted in the conclusion of the contested contract on terms unfavorable to the owner of the robot program. The actions of the robot program shall be presumed to contain the will of its owner, unless proven otherwise. Unauthorized access may be proven, which may be grounds for recognizing the contract as invalid. Therefore, until proven otherwise, the contract must be recognized as containing the true expression of the will of the parties.

It also seems important to consider the procedure and methods of making payments in e-commerce, the legal nature of electronic money and cryptocurrencies, the specifics of making payments with them, and the prospects for civil regulation of making payments in e-commerce.

It should be noted that in modern Uzbekistan a special branch of legislation is being formed that regulates economic relations on the Internet in general, and Electronic Commerce in particular.

The current legislation, despite the presence of general norms of civil law, in the area of regulating relations on the Internet is still at the initial stage of development.

Concluding contracts in e-commerce requires the use of new, unnamed contracts in circulation. Additional complexity to these relationships is often added by the “foreign element”, since the parties to a commercial transaction are often under different jurisdictions.

Electronic commerce is an activity, including professional, aimed at concluding and executing transactions concluded remotely using information systems that do not require notarial and state registration.

Regularly executed transactions (purchase and sale, delivery, performance of work, provision of services) should be considered as the main ones in electronic commerce, while there are also organizational transactions - the organization of electronic commercial turnover and ensuring the execution of basic transactions.

The latter include the following transactions: provision of access services to the information and communication network; organization of various forms of commodity market; provision of services for the formation of electronic commerce tools (for example, the use of electronic digital signatures); implementation of electronic payments; development and use of software; use of various types of communication.

All the above-mentioned transactions are civil law transactions, the peculiarity of which is expressed in the process of conclusion and (or) their execution, the performance of other legally significant actions, and are implemented remotely and with the help of a

special mechanism in electronic data exchange.

An electronic contract is information expressing acceptance to conclude a certain transaction. This information is integral and cannot be changed, i.e. it is recorded and ultimately stored on tangible media. Also, the parties have the ability to properly identify the parties to the contract in any technical and/or organizational way understandable to the counterparty.

The studied legal nature of automated, self-executing contracts, so-called smart contracts, allows us to draw the following conclusions that the legal content is reflected in the form of a formulated and automated execution of the contract using software. The inevitability of the execution of a smart contract arises only upon the occurrence of circumstances previously established by the will-giver, which is ensured by the features of the software environment and/or software. Smart contracts should be classified as special non-independent contractual structures that reflect the specifics of the conclusion or legal consequences of a civil contract. Among the qualifying and legally significant features, it is important to note that the subject of the smart contract is the circulation of digital assets.

As a result of the conducted analysis of the legal nature of electronic commerce, it is necessary to state that the contracts in it are of an exclusively compensated nature, that is, according to Article 355 of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, one party receives payment or other consideration for the performance of its obligations. Moreover, payment under such agreements can be made using various payment instruments.

Analyzing international, foreign, national legislation and business practice, it seems that in order to achieve legal regulation of public relations in the field of electronic commerce, it is necessary to improve the current legislation.

The dynamically developing nature of acts adopted by many international organizations on issues of legal force and features of concluding, executing, terminating cross-border electronic contracts, recognizing electronic document management, taxation of cross-border e-commerce, ensuring rights to intellectual property in the implementation of e-commerce, testifies to the special importance of international cooperation in the harmonization and development of the internal legal systems of individual states.

The issues of theoretical and legislative support for the basic “digital” rights of participants in electronic legal relations, the legal status of subjects of electronic commerce, the civilistic characteristics of digital rights, digital goods, services and big data in the field of electronic commerce are becoming increasingly relevant, electronic transactions and the specifics of their legal regulation in the context of digital transformation of civil turnover, legal basis of personal data and online advertising in the

field of electronic commerce, legal regime of electronic platforms and protection of consumer rights in Internet commerce, payments in electronic commerce, dispute resolution in electronic commerce, international and regional legislation and foreign experience in the field of electronic commerce.

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